

SYSTEMIC TYPOGRAPHY BINUS UNIVERSITY:

A Design Science Research Approach to Institutional Typeface Design**

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ABSTRACT

Systemic typography research aims to strengthen the function of typography as an integrated system within Binus University. Systemic typography is an effort to design letterform expressions by reinforcing the structural formation of letters to function as a document security system, as part of identity strength, and as the primary typographic element in the implementation of both internal and external communication.

This research, which continues with the design of typefaces for Binus University, is motivated by the inconsistency in the use of typefaces across various communication media of Binus University, ranging from web-based digital publications (www.binus.ac.id), social media, lecture presentation materials, including internal publication media and official documents.

Design Science Research (DSR) is the method used in the typeface design process, consisting of three main components: the structural formation of letters, the scaling system of letter structures, and the functional role of typography as an effort to strengthen identity, communication, and document security.

The results of this study are expected to be implemented as an institutional typography standard within Binus University, as a concrete effort to maintain consistency in typeface usage as part of enhancing the value of Binus University, strengthening institutional identity, and serving as an indicator of the authenticity of official Binus University documents.

Keywords: Systemic Typography, Design Science Research, Typeface, Binus University

INTRODUCTION

Binus University, according to data sourced from the Asia University Ranking 2025, is ranked as the best private university in Indonesia, ranked 165 in Asia, and included in the list of the top 851–900 universities in the world. As the best private university in Indonesia, Binus University requires effective communication media, especially as an institution with high complexity in visual communication contexts. Various types of media are continuously utilized to build effective communication both within the internal environment of Binus University and with external stakeholders.

One digital medium considered to have strong potential as a communication bridge in the current era of technological development is web-based and social media platforms, supported by other print media as an effort to build and maintain communication both internally and externally.

Studies related to visual elements, including visual expressions specifically designed for educational institutions, are still limited. This can be observed in the inconsistency found across various visual communication media, including official institutional documents. A concern raised by the researcher is the contradiction within the educational field, where

institutions offering Visual Communication Design programs—where strengthening institutional identity through visual elements is taught—do not fully reflect this knowledge in the actual development of their own institutional identity.

One of the fundamental visual elements in strengthening the identity of an institution is typography, which focuses on the design, selection, and arrangement of letterforms in visual communication media. Based on initial observations conducted by the researcher on Binus University's visual communication media—including print media, indoor and outdoor publications, social media, the website www.binus.ac.id, and official documents—the researcher concludes that Binus University, despite being ranked first in Indonesia, has not fully utilized typography as a means of strengthening identity and as an operational visual system within institutional documents.

Based on these issues, this study attempts to design a typeface for Binus University using a systemic typography approach, further developed through the Design Science Research method. The expected output of this research is a set of Latin alphabet typefaces with characteristics that reflect the institution's vision while strengthening its visual identity through typography.

RESEARCH GAP

Studies in visual communication design, particularly those focusing on typography as a visual element, have been widely conducted. These studies generally focus on aesthetics, readability, and the role of typography in communication. This aligns with Cheng (2005), who states that typography is still primarily positioned within the boundaries of aesthetics and readability. Similarly, Candy and Edmonds (2018) argue that typography research is generally descriptive and exploratory, based on practice-based research.

This systemic typography research identifies three main research gaps:

2.1 Conceptual Gap

Hevner et al. (2007) state that the use of Design Science Research (DSR), which is oriented toward developing artifacts—in this case, typographic expressions as conceptual solutions—is still very limited. Through a DSR approach, it is possible to develop letterforms systematically and measurably, including enhancing their functional and identity value.

2.2 Methodological Gap

The application of typography in visual communication media is generally divided into several functions, including header, subheader, body text, and caption. Design Science Research in this study is not only applied to the aesthetic or informational aspects of typography but is also positioned as a structured system to maintain consistency in letterform construction, which can be further developed into various typographic expressions consistently as an identity system.

2.3 Functional Gap

Typography as a visual element is essential; however, with the implementation of systemic typography and DSR, it is expected that typography will have enhanced functional value in

terms of security and identity, particularly in official institutional documents. The design system will be measurable and stored within the metadata of each character.

SYSTEMIC TYPOGRAPHY AND DESIGN SCIENCE RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

There are three main layers in the typeface design framework using a systemic typography approach:

3.1 Structural Framework of Letterforms

Letterforms are constructed from fundamental visual elements, namely lines. The combination of vertical, horizontal, diagonal, and curved lines produces a complete Latin alphabet set. To achieve balanced visual perception, adjustments in the weight of each line are necessary, including maintaining spatial balance within the letterforms.

The value of typography, as stated by Ambrose and Harris (2011), lies in clarity of form and readability when combined with other letters in words and sentences. However, inconsistent application of line weight can result in imbalance, affecting readability.

Therefore, a system for measuring optical illusion in line quality becomes essential as an integrated system for developing typographic expressions and type families.

3.2 System for Developing Typographic Expression and Typeface Families

The development of typographic expression and typeface families for Binus University is intended to support application across various communication media. This development is carried out systematically based on weight variations, producing type families such as sans-serif light, regular, medium, bold, and extra bold. Additionally, typographic expression development can be extended to other styles such as serif and display fonts, depending on the selected media outputs.

3.3 Application of Typeface Function

The development of typographic expression and type families in this research is limited to digital communication media, such as social media, and print media. However, it also has the potential to be developed further for institutional document security purposes.

DESIGN METHOD

First, the design method begins with identifying problems and analyzing existing typefaces used in media published on www.binus.ac.id, social media @binusuniversityofficial, and printed internal publications.

Second, defining design objectives based on processing limited respondent data from Binus University's academic community regarding their understanding and expectations of typeface characteristics.

Third, designing typographic expressions.

Fourth, digitizing the typeface and its family to ensure usability in computer-based digital systems and applications.

Fifth, implementation and limited usage by internal staff, student organizations, and lecturers.

Sixth, evaluation and documentation of the Binus University typeface usage.

CONCLUSION

This approach is expected to contribute to the development of visual communication design, particularly in the context of system-based typography. The research is expected to be developed as a multi-functional system within an institution. The approach to designing typographic expressions is not limited to consistency of form, while maintaining fundamental principles of Latin typeface design such as clarity and readability, but also adds value and function to strengthen identity and document security.

This study shows that typography can be developed as a multi-functional system within an institutional context. This approach not only improves visual consistency but also supports communication and document security.

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